

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 122

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 122

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 122:0 A Song of Ascents, of David.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 122:1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלוֹת לְדָוִד</p>
<p>Psa. 122:1 I was glad when they said to me, “Let us go to the house of the LORD.”</p> <p>² Our feet are standing Within your gates, O Jerusalem, ³ Jerusalem, that is built As a city that is compact together; ⁴ To which the tribes go up, even the tribes of the LORD — ²An ordinance for Israel — To give thanks to the name of the LORD.</p> <p>⁵ For there thrones were set for judgment, The thrones of the house of David.</p>	<p>שָׂמַחְתִּי בְּאֹמְרֵים לִי בֵּית יְהוָה נִלְכָּד : ² עֲמֻדוֹת הַיָּיִן רַגְלֵינוּ בְּשַׁעְרֵיךָ יְרוּשָׁלַם : ³ יְרוּשָׁלַם הַבְּנוּיָה כְּעִיר שְׂחֻבְרָה-קְלָה יִתְקֶדוּ : ⁴ נְשָׂם עָלוּ שְׂבָטִים שְׂבָטֵי־יְהוָה עֲדוֹת לְיִשְׂרָאֵל לְהָדוֹת לְשֵׁם יְהוָה : ⁵ כִּי שָׁמָּה אֵינְשָׁבוּ כְּסֵאוֹת לְמִשְׁפַּט כְּסֵאוֹת לְבֵית דָּוִד : ⁶ שָׂאוּ שְׁלוֹם יְרוּשָׁלַם יִשְׁלְיוּ אֶהְבִּיבֶךָ : ⁷ יְהִי־ שְׁלוֹם בְּחֵילֶךָ שְׁלוֹהָ בְּאַרְמְנוֹתֶיךָ : ⁸ לְמַעַן אֶתִּי וְרַעֲי אֶדְבָּרָה־נָּא שְׁלוֹם בְּךָ : ⁹ לְמַעַן בֵּית־יְהוָה אֶלְהֵינוּ אֶבְקֶשָׁה טוֹב לָךְ :</p>
<p>Psa. 122:6 Pray for the peace of Jerusalem: “May they prosper who love you. ⁷ “May peace be within your walls, And prosperity within your palaces.” ⁸ For the sake of my brothers and my friends, I will now say, “May peace be within you.” ⁹ For the sake of the house of the LORD our God, I will seek your good.</p>	<p>שָׁמָּה אֵינְשָׁבוּ כְּסֵאוֹת לְמִשְׁפַּט כְּסֵאוֹת לְבֵית דָּוִד : ⁶ שָׂאוּ שְׁלוֹם יְרוּשָׁלַם יִשְׁלְיוּ אֶהְבִּיבֶךָ : ⁷ יְהִי־ שְׁלוֹם בְּחֵילֶךָ שְׁלוֹהָ בְּאַרְמְנוֹתֶיךָ : ⁸ לְמַעַן אֶתִּי וְרַעֲי אֶדְבָּרָה־נָּא שְׁלוֹם בְּךָ : ⁹ לְמַעַן בֵּית־יְהוָה אֶלְהֵינוּ אֶבְקֶשָׁה טוֹב לָךְ :</p>

References

Psalm 122:1

^aPs 42:4; Is 2:3; Mic 4:2; Zech 8:21

Psalm 122:2

^aPs 9:14; 87:2; 116:19; Jer 7:2

Psalm 122:3

^aPs 48:13; 147:2

^b2 Sam 5:9; Neh 4:6

Psalm 122:4

¹Heb *YAH*

²Or *A testimony*

^aEx 23:17; Deut 16:16; Ps 84:5

Psalm 122:5

^aDeut 17:8; 2 Chr 19:8; Ps 89:29

Psalm 122:6

^aPs 29:11; Jer 29:7

^bPs 102:14

Psalm 122:7

^aPs 51:18; Is 62:6

^bPs 48:3, 13; Jer 17:27

Psalm 122:8

^aPs 133:1

^b1 Sam 25:6; John 20:19

Psalm 122:9

^aNeh 2:10; Esth 10:3

Targum

Psa. 122:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. I rejoiced with those who say to me, "Let us go to the sanctuary of the LORD."² Our feet were standing in your gates, O Jerusalem.³ Jerusalem that is built in the firmament is like a city that has been joined together on earth.⁴ Unto which the tribes have gone up, the tribes of the LORD, he who testifies to Israel that his presence abides among them when they go to give thanks to the name of the LORD.⁵ For there thrones have been placed; in Jerusalem thrones are in the sanctuary for the kings of the house of David.⁶ Seek the welfare of Jerusalem; those who love you will dwell in tranquillity.⁷ Let there be peace in your armies, tranquillity in your citadels.⁸ On account of my brothers and companions, I will now speak in you of peace.⁹ Because of the sanctuary of the LORD our God, I will seek to do good to you.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm describes the glory of Jerusalem of old. In ancient days, cities generally remained small. Jerusalem on the other hand grew and grew. It was a place that a Jew could have a personal encounter with the LORD. That experience was a personal dramatic revelation which touched a different part of the soul. The different people who came to Jerusalem demonstrated the diversity of the LORD's creation. No one was concerned about skin color or nationality. If you came to Jerusalem to experience the LORD, especially when the Temples existed, the traveler was shown hospitality and immediate acceptance.

Notes of the Psalm

In ancient days the people of Jerusalem truly followed the Torah. Hospitality was a mainstay of Semitic life. Nationality or race was not a concern to the people. The Children of Israel were descendants of Jacob and there were twelve tribes. All tribes of Israel were welcomed in Jerusalem. Also, people from all over the world who wanted to experience the love and grace of the LORD were welcomed. The Temple's outer court was especially designated for the non-Jew. These people had access to the LORD there. Many Jews came to the Temple and from the Gentile Court also felt the presence of the LORD. It was a time of acceptance of all people. Unfortunately, that is not what is happening today. The world would be much better off if the attitude of full acceptance and hospitality came back to the world.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

